

ESiWACE3 Newsletter

Issue #8 / May 2025

News

Announcing the 2nd ESIWACE3 Summer School: hpc4Climate

We are excited to announce that the second ESIWACE3 Summer School is set to take place from July 28 – August 7, 2025, in the historic town of Lauenburg, Germany!

Organized jointly by ESIWACE3 and the German BMBF project WarmWorld, the hpc4Climate Summer School aims to bring together young researchers and software engineers eager to explore cutting-edge technological advancements in climate modeling and high-performance computing (HPC).

This will be an **on-site event** in the historic town of Lauenburg, up the Elbe River from Hamburg, with no possibility of remote participation. Participants will attend **lectures** and **hands-on** sessions that will guide them through the fundamentals of running weather and climate simulations on modern HPC systems, as well as managing and analysing Earth system model data.

The programme is aimed at **Masters** and **early PhD students** in Computer Science, Data Science, Techno-Mathematics, Applied Mathematics, as well as students from Meteorology and Climate Science with programming skills and an interest in scientific computing. Women and participants from ITC countries are particularly encouraged to apply for the Summer School!

All details about the school, including the conditions for application, can be found on the school's website: <https://hpc4climate2025.org/>

Deadline for applications: 30 April 2025

3rd ESIWACE3 Hackathon

On 21–23 October 2025, the 3rd **ESIWACE3 Hackathon** will take place at the Jülich Supercomputing Centre (JSC) in Jülich, Germany.

Titled “Porting Earth System Models to the First EuroHPC Exascale System (JUPITER),” this event supports **researchers and developers preparing their Earth System Models (ESMs) for Europe's first exascale supercomputer.**

The hackathon will be **hybrid**, with in-person participation strongly encouraged. At least one team member must attend in person, though others may join remotely if needed.

Participants will bring their code and collaborate with High-Performance Computing (HPC) experts to optimize and port climate and weather models for JUPITER, featuring NVIDIA GH200 Grace Hopper Superchips. The focus areas include performance optimization, portability, and scalability on exascale systems.

Eligible applicants must be from EuroHPC Joint Undertaking or Inclusiveness Target Countries. Teams of two to four members, with a mix of expertise in Earth system modeling and HPC, are encouraged to apply. Preference is given to open-source projects and early-career scientists.

Teams must submit a short proposal outlining their project, challenges, and expected outcomes. The application deadline is 30 June 2025, with notifications by 15 July 2025.

A €1500 prize, sponsored by HPC services provider [Do It Now](#), will support the winning team's attendance at a European academic conference.

For details and registration, visit the event website or apply via <https://forms.office.com/r/RiC1BiCZRb>. For inquiries, contact l.zou@fz-juelich.de or l.hoffmann@fz-juelich.de.

We look forward to seeing you in Jülich!

The banner features the ESIWACE logo at the top left, the Jülich Forschungszentrum logo in the top center, and the Do It Now logo at the top right. The main title "3RD ESIWACE3 HACKATHON" is prominently displayed in large, bold, teal letters. Below it, the subtitle "Porting Earth System Models to the First EuroHPC Exascale System (JUPITER)" is written in white. The background includes a stylized globe with a color gradient from blue to red, a circular inset showing a town, and various technical icons like a location pin and a calendar. At the bottom, the location "Jülich Supercomputing Centre Jülich (Germany)" and the date "21-23 October 2025" are provided, along with the text "Hybrid format".

ESiWACE3 Launches New Guidelines to Foster Inclusion and Diversity in Earth System Modelling and HPC Events

The ESiWACE3 project has taken a step toward building a more inclusive and diverse community within Earth system modelling and high-performance computing (HPC). In line with its commitment to gender and geographical diversity, ESiWACE3 has developed a guideline aimed at promoting equity and creating a welcoming environment for all participants in its events and training.

The newly introduced guidelines provide practical advice for planning, organizing, and running inclusive events. The initiative reflects ESiWACE3's focus on fostering a culture where everyone feels valued and encouraged to contribute, regardless of background.

ESiWACE3 sees these guidelines as a work in progress and welcomes feedback from the community. Every suggestion and experience shared will help make future events even more inclusive and reflective of the diverse voices in the field.

To access the full guidelines and contribute your feedback, visit [here](#).

 #ESIWACE311F

Promoting inclusiveness in ESiWACE3 training and events

ESiWACE3 aims to **foster engagement strategies** that promote equity, focusing on gender and geographical diversity. We have developed a checklist to help event organizers ensure ESiWACE3 events are open, welcoming, and beneficial to all.

Key points to help plan more inclusive events:

- ✓ Ensure that the organising team is **diverse** and includes people from **under-represented groups**.
- ✓ Collaborate with **existing initiatives and networks** to identify and connect with diverse presenters.
- ✓ Ask for all **relevant information** at registration: e.g. dietary needs, accessibility needs and preferred name and pronouns.
- ✓ Make sure that the venue is **physically accessible** to all.

* Please note that this guide will be in constant evolution.

Mid-Term ESIWACE3 Work Package Video Series!

During the 3rd General Assembly of ESIWACE3, held in November 2024 in Hamburg, our consortium gathered to assess the progress made halfway through the project. After two years of collaboration, this in-person meeting provided the perfect opportunity to reflect on our achievements, explore future directions, and engage with key stakeholders in the weather and climate modelling community.

As part of this milestone, we recorded a series of short interviews with the leaders of each of our six Work Packages, plus a video regarding our compression data lab. In these videos, they share firsthand insights into the goals, challenges, and key results of their work, showing how, after two years, ESIWACE3 is advancing high-performance computing (HPC) technologies for weather and climate applications in Europe.

Watch all the videos [here!](#)

ESIWACE3 Showcased at EuroHPC Summit 2025 in Kraków

From 18–20 March 2025, the EuroHPC Summit gathered more than 1,000 experts, professionals, students, and enthusiasts in Kraków, Poland—marking a record attendance for this flagship event of the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking.

ESIWACE3 was proudly present, engaging with the HPC community through a dedicated poster presentation in the EuroHPC Poster Sessions. Our display highlighted the mission and impact of ESIWACE3 in enhancing weather and climate modelling via high-performance computing—a topic that resonated strongly in a summit rich with discussion on AI, quantum computing, and HPC innovation.

A key highlight for ESIWACE3 was the participation of our Principal Investigator, **Mario Acosta**, in a round table discussion titled *“Boosting the Applications Ecosystem in the Future.”* His contribution underscored the importance of co-design, scalability, and application readiness in the evolving EuroHPC landscape.

We are grateful to the EuroHPC JU for the opportunity to contribute and connect, and we look forward to continuing our mission within this dynamic and growing community.

ESiWACE3 at HiPEAC 2025: Towards gender balance at HPC

During the HiPEAC Conference in Barcelona, ESiWACE3 co-organized two full-day workshops aimed at discussing the current status of HPC applications in Europe and the ongoing collaborative efforts to enhance their scalability.

The organizing team focused on gathering contributions from various European Centres of Excellence (CoEs) and other relevant projects. Special attention was given to gender balance when inviting speakers, reflecting a commitment to inclusivity and diversity in the HPC community.

As a result, the program featured:

- 22 technical talks
- 1 panel discussion
- 2 live demos

These sessions showcased contributions from 11 of the 12 active CoEs, as well as representatives from Destination Earth, EPICURE, ENES, CASTIEL-2, and the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking.

Notably, the speaker distribution was 74% female, 22% male, and 4% non-binary.

The workshops were well attended, with 25 to 30 participants per session, and they generated lively, in-depth discussions between speakers and the audience.

Even more encouraging was the gender balance among attendees: 56% women and 44% men.

Considering that the typical gender distribution at this event tends to be 10–20% women and 80–90% men, this shift represents a remarkable achievement.

If you want to check further data and results, read the full news [here](#).

Events

External events

External events in which ESiWACE3 has participated since the last issue of the ESiWACE Newsletter:

- [Code Performance Analysis with Extrae and Paraver training](#), 27 January 2025. Training. Organization. Online
- [HiPEAC Conference](#), 20-22 February 2025. Round table. Organization. Booth
- [E-Science Days](#), Heidelberg (Germany), 12.-14. March 2025. [Presentation](#)
- [EuroHPC Summit](#), Krakow(Poland), 18-21. March 2025. [Poster](#) and round table.
- [2025 InPEX Workshop](#), Tokyo (Japan), 15-17. April 2025. Presentation.

- [EGU25](#), Vienna (Austria), 27 April 2 May.

News from the neighbours

Upcoming conferences and events

- [ISC High Performance 2025](#), 10-13 June 2025, Hamburg (Germany)

Training events

Find collected information on upcoming and past training events from all consortium partners and projects we are involved with [here](#).